

ISic3529

I.Sicily inscription 3529

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis at the Orti della Maddalena

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3577

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI313651

1. Θ (εοῖς) Κ (αταχθονίοις)
2. Κλ (ωδία) □ Ρωμαντίλ-
3. λα □ ἔζ (ησεν) □ ἔτ (η) □ δ' □ μ (ἦνας) □ η'
4. ἦμ (έρας) □ ιδ' □ Κλ (ώδιος) □ Θησ-
5. εὺς □ π[ατ]ήρ □ τέκ (νω) □ γλυκυτ (άτω) .
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493861

EDCS 38200015

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Bibliography

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